

Improving Delay Wire Chamber Performance Using Electronegative Gases

ABILMANSUR RAKHMETTULAYEV, TARGYN FAIZULLA,
BIRLIK YESSEN, YELKHAN ZHAPPAS, ALDIYAR
KANAT, ALIASKAR ZHILKIBAYEV,

TEAM XERCES

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1) Introduction

Physicists have been using gaseous particle detectors for a very long time. Among these devices, the Delay Wire Chamber (DWC) has emerged as one of the most efficient tools due to its simplified design, higher resolution, and faster response as compared to the traditional Multi Wire Proportional Chamber (MWPC). However, further advancements for the DWC performance are possible.

DWCs use a gas mixture of Ar/CO_2 , as it is a safe and environmentally friendly option with a sufficient gas gain. However, we propose a novel gas mixture that surpasses the Ar/CO_2 mixture in many aspects. Our gas would not only be ecologically sustainable, but also significantly more efficient, unlocking a new level of performance for DWCs.

In our experiment, we aim to find the optimal concentration of the gases. If successful, it will improve DWC particle detection for generations to come.

Figure 1: Diagram of the electric field inside the DWC [1; p.1]

2) Motivation

The Beamline for Schools competition is an excellent teamwork opportunity. We are a team of Kazakh students that sees this competition as a way to channel our teamwork into a real-life, actionable research setting. We have long dreamt of delving into research, performing experiments, and contributing to this field, and we are excited to turn this into reality. This experience will both propel our project and inspire students from all over our country to pursue similar challenges and develop their potential as future physicists.

3) Aim of the experiment

We aim to introduce a new type of gas to the DWC, as we hypothesize that it will increase the chamber's performance. We will add our gas to the DWC, then measure and quantify the detector's gas gain, space and time resolution, detection efficiency, and noise levels, which will be compared to those of the basic DWC gas mixture.

4) Background theory

4.1) Our proposed gas

DWCs use a mixture of Argon (50%)/Carbon Dioxide (50%) due to its safety, and also because it is a good compromise between being inoffensive and having great gas gain. But 'magic gas' mixtures may be used instead to enhance the chamber [1], which allows the detector to achieve even higher gas gain, faster response, better efficiency, etc [2].

We propose to combine the current DWC gas with the concept of the 'magic gas', while also staying environmentally friendly; we will achieve this by adding an electronegative component. Our gas mixture consists of an ionizing gas, a quencher gas and an electronegative gas, each with a specific function:

- **Argon (ionizing gas):** allows charged particles to create Townsend avalanches [3].

where X is the ionizing gas atom

p is the charged particle entering the detector

- **Carbon dioxide (the quencher gas):** absorbs excess photons emitted by excited argon ions that could trigger unwanted avalanches.

- **R-1234ze (electronegative gas):** effectively captures free electrons. This limits their lifetime and prevents them from causing secondary avalanches, leading to more precise peaks. Moreover, freon limits the sensitive area of the anode wires, effectively neutralizing the effects of space charge. This allows us to get the aforementioned benefits of the magic gas.
- **NovectTM5110:** Required to make full use of R-1234ze [4]

Historically, Freon-13B1 was used as the electronegative gas in magic gas mixtures. However, Freon is highly dangerous for the environment, with a Global Warming Potential (GWP) of 6900.

Because of this, we decided to replace it with an eco-friendly option: a mixture of R-1234ze with a small percentage of NovecTM5110. R-1234ze is a highly electronegative, non-flammable gas that consists of HFO-1234ze, with a GWP of around 6 [5]. It has been studied for use in Resistive Plate Chambers (RPC), and has showed results which were similar to Freon R-134a, another type of Freon gas.

This gas has limitations without the addition of SF_6 [4], but SF_6 has a GWP of 23900, which is why we replaced it with NovecTM5110, which is a sustainable alternative to SF_6 , with GWP less than 1. NovecTM5110 is also a highly electronegative and non-flammable gas, so no threat will be posed to the detector.

4.2) Impact of the electronegative gas

The addition of an electronegative gas affects several characteristics that directly impact the performance of the DWC.

- **Gas gain:** The amplification of the original signal. Electronegative gases affect the gas gain as they neutralize the effect of space charge, adding an additional factor of 100 to the pulse height [6]. The addition of such gases showed that even the smallest charges could be detected.

Figure 2: Avalanche sizes with different percentages of the electronegative gas [7; p.2]

- **Spatial resolution:** The ability of a detector to accurately measure the position of the particle depends on various factors, such as the diffusion of charges. This linear distribution of charges after a diffusing time t can be described by:

$$\frac{dN}{dx} = \frac{N_0}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{4Dt}\right)$$

where N_0 is the total number of charges,

x is the distance from the point of creation,

D is the diffusion coefficient.

The diffusion coefficient depends on several factors of the chamber gas, including its mass:

$$D = \frac{2}{3\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{P\sigma_0} \sqrt{\frac{(kT)^3}{m}}$$

where T is the temperature,

P is the pressure,

m is the mass of the gas particle.

Meaning that the parameters of the chamber gas will affect the diffusion, consequently affecting space resolution.

Figure 3: Space resolution with different concentrations of the electronegative gas [2]

- **Time resolution:** The ability of a detector to measure the timing of events depends on the drift velocity of the charges. The drift velocity is related to the diffusion coefficient through the formula:

$$\frac{D}{\mu} = \frac{kT}{e}$$

where μ equals:

$$\mu = \frac{u}{E}$$

u is the drift velocity,

E is the electric field strength.

Evidently, the choice of gas will affect the timing resolution of the detector.

- **Efficiency:** The probability of detecting a particle upon entering the detector. Studies have shown that when the percentage of the electronegative

gas exceeds a certain amount, the efficiency starts to rapidly decrease, as shown in Figure 4. It means that we need to carefully choose our percentage of the electronegative gas in the mixture.

Figure 4: Efficiency with different electronegative gas percentages [6; p.10]

5) Experiment design

5.1) Setup

Figure 5: Our setup for measuring the DWC performance

All the experiments in 5.2 will be done with the following setup: Two scintillators (S0 and S1) with photomultiplier (PMT) tubes will be connected to an AND gate located upstream, and a DWC will be connected to an oscilloscope located downstream. The DWC will be activated through a trigger mechanism. The distance between S0 and S1 should be the same as the distance between S1 and the DWC. The energy of the T9 proton beam will be operating at a constant 2 GeV.

5.2) Gas percentage variation

The goal of our experiments will be to test our proposed gas mixtures with various gas ratios.

- 1) First, we will keep a balance of Argon 45% and Carbon Dioxide 45% to keep the original 1:1 ratio, and then try to find the ideal balance of R-1234ze and NovecTM5110 (where they are 10% together). We will start with 0% of NovecTM5110 to see what happens without it, and then go up to 5% with a step of 0.5%.
- 2) After finding the ideal balance in 1., we will increase the concentration of the electronegative component in the chamber gas. Every experiment in

5.3 will be tested percentages 0, 0.5, 1, 5, 10 and 20 percent to find the biggest values for the characteristics in 4.2

5.3) Experiments in detail

- 1) To find the gas gain, we will vary the voltage applied to the DWC within its operating limit (around 2500 to 2900V) to find the largest value for the gas gain/pulse height.
- 2) Additionally, we want to see how the gas mixture will affect noise levels. For that we want to turn on the chamber without the beam and see whether the noise levels will change in order to calculate the signal-to-noise ratio. The experiment will be performed in a similar fashion to the gas gain experiment.
- 3) To calculate the space resolution we will use a secondary detector system made of two scintillators to precisely measure the location of the particle.

As the scintillators are connected to an AND gate, they will only register the particles that are heading in a straight direction without any significant deviation, and are thus most likely to have the same location upon entering the DWC. We then compare this with the location data of the DWC.

Scintillation counters were chosen for their high quality space resolution of 100 μm

- 4) Time resolution - the distance between S0 and S1 will be the same as the distance between S1 and the DWC. We will turn on all three detectors at the same time, so that the time of flight of a particle between S0 and S1 should be the same as the time between S1 and the DWC. Knowing that, we could compare the two times of flight to measure the margin of error of the time resolution of the DWC.

Scintillation counters have an excellent time resolution of 100 ps, making them excellent for this task.

- 5) For calculating the efficiency, we will use the same AND gate system used in the space resolution experiment so that a particle will be counted only if it will be detected in both scintillators to find the total number of particles exiting the beam. Then we will divide this number by the number of particles detected in the DWC.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{n_d}{N_T}$$

where ε = the detection efficiency of a detector

n_d = the detected number of events in a detector

N_T = the total number of events that took place in the detector

- 6) We also want to see whether our gas mixture will age the wires of the chamber, affecting its behaviour. For that, we will expose the chamber for several hours to a high intensity β radiation source. This should be equivalent to several months of non-stop operation [6]. Then, we will perform our performance experiments again, to see if we notice any changes.

6) Schedule

Days	Experiments
1-2	Create the set up
3	Gas gain and noise experiment
4	Spatial resolution experiment
5	Time resolution experiment
6	Efficiency experiment
7-8	Wire aging experiment

Table 1: Our schedule

The following days are going to be used for data collection, analysis, and additional runs.

7) What we hope to take away from the experience

We have long dreamt of creating fulfilling research. This is an exquisite opportunity to do so. However, we hope to not only fulfill that wish, but also to make a direct improvement in the field of particle physics; our project has a direct scientific application. In doing so, we, most of all, hope to leave an impact, and make the world of science a slightly better one. We hope to take away knowledge about experiment design, particle physics, and also have the opportunity to work with the best experts in the field.

8) Outreach

We firmly believe that knowledge should be open to all. It is the utmost priority to share valuable information with others, which is why we are participating in Beamline For Schools Competition. We will film a video series of our time at CERN in four languages: Russian, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Uzbek, as we have team members who speak them. The videos will show the research process, interspersed with beautiful footage of Geneva. We want to inspire young physicists all over Central Asia, which is why we are making the video in four languages. Most of all, we want to show to aspiring scientists that their dreams can also come true.

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